

Transforming to a regenerative farming system in Yorkshire

Summary report of the co-creative Three Horizons process

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Summary

The current mainstream food system is contributing to social and environmental crises. Something must change so that the food system works regeneratively, but this is a huge challenge with many different actors and complexities to consider. Food production is one part of the food system where there are opportunities to transform to a system that is working regeneratively.

To gain a deeper understanding of the actions needed to transform to a regenerative farming system, FixOurFood carried out a survey and workshops in 2022 with a diverse range of practitioners and researchers involved in the Yorkshire farming system.

The 'Three Horizons' method was used to guide the discussions, as it provides a useful framework in workshop settings to structure a deeper analysis. Three Horizons explores the current system, the desired future and actions needed to support the transformation. In this report we summarise the discussions and actions raised during this process.

Key discussion points

The current food system: many traditional conventional farming methods are degrading the local and global environment. These methods can also be financially precarious and lacking in resilience, yet there is little incentive or support to transform practice, including a lack of evidence-based practice. There are cycles related to financial precarity making transformation risky, and declining soil quality increases dependence on high inputs to maintain yields but further degrades soils' long-term potential.

The desired future: food producers have embraced agricultural practices which regenerate the environment and regenerative farming systems have been embedded in local communities. As well as food, farms also produce a wide range of non-food public services. Farmers are well rewarded and incentivised to produce food in this way via supply chains and government support. There is also high awareness and connectivity of food system actors.

There are already growing disruptions and innovations that could support transformation, including increasing interest and research in regenerative farming, supportive organisations and knowledge-sharing events, a retail drive for more sustainable produce, and high input costs encouraging farmers to adopt less intensive practice. However, much more action is needed.

Key areas of action required to support a transformative shift towards regenerative farming include: building stronger farmer sharing networks; providing unbiased, respectful support to farmers transforming their practice, including a strong research evidence base; developing stronger market incentives for sustainable farming; improving the farmer-policy relationship; and shifting public perspectives of good food.

Small pockets of our desired future already exist today. There are many farmers in Yorkshire and beyond who are already implementing innovative regenerative practices and taking greater control of their supply chains, and forward-thinking support organisations encouraging this transformation. There are also restaurants and other businesses supporting local and seasonal food. Connecting and growing these initiatives will be key to mainstreaming a regenerative food system.

Background

The challenge

Our current food systems underpin many **social and environmental crises**, including food poverty, obesity, climate change, pollution and accelerating biodiversity loss.

There is increasing recognition that simply tweaking the current system (e.g. improving efficiency) is insufficient to address these crises, and that a **more fundamental transformation** is essential: changing values, mindsets, paradigms and narratives.

Moreover, many aspects of planetary and human health have already passed critical thresholds, so simply **reducing further harm is also insufficient**.

Instead, we need **regenerative food systems** that 'spiral up' social and environmental benefits and restore human and environmental wellbeing.

A core challenge is therefore finding ways to **steward transformations** towards **regenerative futures**. The FixOurFood project focuses on Yorkshire as a pilot region for exploring how such transformations could be enabled.

The importance of farming systems

The way food is produced is a core aspect of the wider food system that will need to be part of the transformation towards a more regenerative system.

Transformation of farming systems is critical as they are a major contributor to biodiversity loss and climate change, and have a huge influence on land use. At the same time, the universal importance of farming systems for meeting human needs makes them fundamental for transforming wider food systems.

Aims

The principal aim was to generate conversations and discussions around **envisioning desired futures and highlighting critical actions** required for transformational change.

We discussed the question: 'How can Yorkshire's farming system be transformed, so that regenerative farming practices become mainstream to meet the current and future needs of people and planet?'

Within this broad question, the work aimed to identify, in the context of Yorkshire's farming system:

- current challenges;
- desired futures;
- critical actions needed to support transformation;
- inspirational practice already existing currently in Yorkshire.

The work is one of three parallel processes undertaken as part of **FixOurFood**, a £6M five-year project funded by the UKRI Transforming Food Systems Strategic Priorities Fund, which aims to understand how to steward transformations towards a regenerative food system in Yorkshire and beyond.

Approach

A series of surveys and online workshops were held in 2022 with experts working in and researching the Yorkshire farming system, using the **Three Horizons** futures method, to co-create strategic insights about how to support transformation.

Three Horizons was chosen for this purpose for a number of reasons:

- it is a simple yet powerful method of dealing with complexity and uncertainty in a way that fosters a sense of hope;
- it develops the skill of conceptualising how the envisioned future can emerge from the present (so-called futures consciousness);
- it explicitly distinguishes between transformative change and more gradual change or change that continues the status quo;
- it identifies where power lies in systems;
- and it fosters empathy for different mindsets, creating a space where a diverse range of participants can convene to constructively share their different perspectives,.

Three Horizons centres around a framework of three overlapping 'horizons', each representing a pattern in the way things are done:

- **Horizon 1 (H1)** is the current pattern that must be transformed to align to a changing world;
- **Horizon 3 (H3)** is the desired future pattern;
- **Horizon 2 (H2)** are the innovations, initiatives and actions that can potentially foster and create space for the desired future (H3).

Via a questionnaire and online workshops, participants explored their personal and collective understanding of:

- the challenges in the current farming system (H1);
- the desired future (H3);
- the transformative action (H2) needed to get to that future;
- what current (H1) aspects we wish to keep or amplify in the future (H3);
- what actors and practice embodying aspects of the future (H3) already exist in the present, providing hope and inspiration.

Following an initial 2-hour online onboarding meeting to explain the process that would follow, participants completed a five-question open-ended questionnaire structured around the five aspects listed above. FixOurFood researchers thematically clustered the survey responses in Mural, an online collaborative whiteboard tool (<https://www.mural.co/>). The clustered survey results were then collaboratively explored and refined in two online workshops (2 and 3 hours long), each with 6-7 FixOurFood researchers and c. 7-10 external stakeholders, using Mural to record the outcomes of the discussions. In the first workshop we explored and refined the results for H1 and H3 from the survey and reflected on the shift in values between them. In the second workshop we focused on the results for H2, identified areas of strength and weakness in current H2 action, and finished by revisiting the inspirational 'pockets of the future in the present' in the Yorkshire food system (e.g. farmers already using regenerative practices).

The outcome of this process is a collective understanding of how actions can more effectively support systemic transformation.

This report summarises the topics and actions discussed throughout this Three Horizons process. The report's intention is to summarise the discussions for future reference and to guide further discussions, rather than to provide a comprehensive review of the food system.

Three Horizons map

Summary narrative

Horizon 1 Present challenges

Conventional farming methods are degrading the local and global environment

- There is a 'conventional' farming mindset focused on high yields
- Traditional conventional farming methods create a cycle of soil degradation
- Conventional farming can be financially precarious and lacking in resilience
- There is little incentive or support for farmers to transform practice

Horizon 2 Supporting transformation

Support regenerative farming systems with knowledge, infrastructure and incentives

- Build stronger networks of sharing best practice
- Provide unbiased, respectful technological and logistical support to farmers transforming their practice
- Ensure stronger retail incentives for sustainable farming
- Improving the farmer-policy relationship is nonetheless important
- Shift public perspectives of good food

Horizon 3 Our desired future

Regenerative farming systems are embraced and embedded in local communities

- Food producers have embraced viable farming practices that produce food whilst regenerating environmental health
- Farms also produce a wide range of non-food public services
- Farmers are well rewarded and incentivised to produce food in this way
- There is high awareness and connectivity of food system actors

Horizon 1: present challenges

Conventional farming methods are degrading the local and global environment

To understand H1, participants identified problems with the current Yorkshire farming system that prevent it from meeting the needs of people and planet.

Participants identified the dominance of a **'conventional' farming mindset focused on high yields**, featuring monocropping, limited rotations, tilling, and high inputs (e.g. fertiliser and pesticides) that are carbon-intensive, reduce biodiversity, and can increase flood risk and reduce water quality. Such practices are especially prevalent in contracts that do not support long-term stewardship of the land. Moreover, regenerative farming methods produce what are traditionally considered to be lower-quality products and reduced yields that could cause equity issues, and outsource environmental damage overseas.

Of particular concern is that **conventional farming methods generate a reinforcing cycle of soil degradation**, with declining soil quality increasing dependence on high inputs to maintain yields, further degrading soils' long-term potential.

Conventional farming can also be financially precarious and lacking in resilience, especially due to high input costs, and many farmers feel like victims of supply chains, which in Yorkshire are currently controlled by a relatively small number of large companies. This restricts farmers' agency and makes transformation too risky, entrenching conventional practice. The increase in frequency of extreme weather events due to climate change further increases financial precarity.

There is little incentive or support for farmers to transform practice. Awareness of better practice is held back by factors including a lack of feasibility and impact studies for regenerative practice, and paywalled data. Government policy considers sustainable farming as an after-thought, innovation is too slow and under-funded, and subsidy payments tend to concentrate in landowners' hands rather than farmers'. There is mistrust and frustration towards the government after years of changing policies and difficult systems to navigate. Farmers have unequal access to enabling technology such as digital connectivity in rural areas.

In summary, in H1 **conventional farming methods are degrading the local and global environment**. Participants identified reinforcing cycles related to soil degradation and financial precarity making transformation too risky.

Nonetheless, mainstream aspects of H1 were identified as being helpful to maintain or even amplify in the future. These include family farms with their long-term stewardship approach, strong Yorkshire brand awareness, and the heritage value of the Yorkshire landscape.

Horizon 3: the desired future

Regenerative farming systems are embraced and embedded in local communities

To understand H3, participants imagined looking around them in 2050 and identifying evidence that a transformation of Yorkshire's farming system has taken place, such that it now meets current and future needs of people and planet, with regenerative farming systems the mainstream.

Participants envisioned that in H3, **food producers have been supported to embrace viable farming practices that produce food whilst regenerating environmental health.** Food is produced extensively and efficiently in regenerative farming systems, with a high diversity of crops and livestock, a focus on high-value, high-quality, low-intensity crops tailored to Yorkshire's (changing) environmental conditions, with minimal waste. Consumers understand and accept new realities of food choice, including seasonality, which is important for Yorkshire's increased self-sufficiency. Any food imports match Yorkshire quality standards.

Farms also produce a wide range of non-food public services. Food production is carbon-negative, and farms use 100% renewable energy and produce energy on-farm. Farms therefore become off-grid units supplying energy to immediate communities. Farms also support high biodiversity, and soil and water quality. The wellbeing of both producers and consumers is therefore increasing.

Farmers are well rewarded and incentivised to produce food in this way.

They are less dependent on government support because their produce is valued appropriately in supply chains, including by supermarkets that make their healthy, sustainable food universally accessible to local communities at affordable prices. Nonetheless, government funding is important for supporting a 'public money for public goods' approach to farming and ensuring competitiveness with imported produce.

There is high awareness and connectivity of food system actors. There is close communication between farmers, academia and policy, and a culture of sharing best practice between farmers, with a global network of farm data-sharing. A reconnection of people to nature is integral to food and farming education, with stronger links between urban and rural areas.

In summary, in H3 **regenerative farming systems are embraced and embedded in local communities.**

Pockets of this future already exist today. Participants identified many farmers in Yorkshire and beyond who are already implementing innovative regenerative agricultural practices and taking greater control of their supply chains, and forward-thinking support organisations encouraging this kind of transformation. There are also restaurants and other businesses supporting local and seasonal food.

Value shift between H1 and H3

The transformative shift from H1 to H3 can be considered a shift in underlying values that needs to occur. Participants identified various examples of these value shifts for the H1 and H3 that they had described.

H1 value	H3 value
Regenerative agriculture too risky - financially and for ensuring food security and equity	Regenerative farming systems are the inspiring choice for practitioners
Farming decisions focus on yield to drive profit	Farming decisions are backed financially to improve livelihoods and resilience rather than solely yield
Production heavily commodified - just a few main crops	Production is tailored to place - therefore a greater diversity of crops
Practitioners are isolated from each other	Culture of networking, sharing best practice, data, equipment, etc.
Good practice is not given appropriate recognition	Awareness and recognition of what good practice is
Consumers used to full freedom of choice and yet have a restricted diet	Consumers are adventurous and embrace new realities of choice associated with food produced in regenerative systems (e.g. more seasonality and Yorkshire-produced food) - becomes a standard that is demanded
Farming is not seen as a desirable career for an increasing number of young people due to concern about farming challenges	Young people and innovators are highly motivated to enter the farming sector and are amply supported to do so

Horizon 2: supporting transformation

Support
regenerative
farming systems
with knowledge,
infrastructure
and incentives

To understand H2, participants identified current initiatives, or initiatives that are needed, that could help to facilitate the transformative shift from H1 to H3. Participants also identified domains of H2 where good progress is already being made, and domains of H2 where there is insufficient progress and/or currently a lack of action.

Participants identified that **there are already growing disruptions and innovations that could support transformation**, including increasing interest and research in regenerative farming systems, support organisations and knowledge-sharing events, a retail drive for more sustainable produce, and high input costs encouraging farmers to adopt less intensive practice. However, much more action is needed.

According to the participants, there is a need in H2 to **build stronger networks of sharing best practice**, specialist farm equipment, and the benefits (including financial) from farming regeneratively. Showcasing events should be targeted to relevant landscapes, and prioritise farmers' voices.

Unbiased, respectful technological and logistical support should be provided to farmers transforming their practice, e.g. in the form of technologies for resource recovery from waste streams, workable alternatives to traditional inputs, improved communications connection in rural areas and an independent scientific evidence base for the impacts of regenerative farming. Supporting more rapid responses of farmers to their (often abundant) on-farm data can speed up feedbacks in farmers' business decisions.

There must be stronger market incentives for sustainable farming. Supply chains must be reconfigured, supporting more direct sales, local and seasonal sourcing, and twinned urban and rural farms to establish community links. Supermarkets and food processors should pay farmers supporting regeneration on their farms a fair price and modify their quality standards (e.g. accepting more 'wonky veg') to cut food waste. Differential lending should be introduced for investments in regenerative farming systems.

Improving the farmer-policy relationship is nonetheless important. Government representatives need a more active local presence to rebuild trust with farmers. ELMS could be transformative but only with attractive payment rates that have a whole farm system rather than field parcel basis, commitment to long-term planning and payments, simple and well-explained funding opportunities supported by user-friendly application systems, and more investment in knowledge transfer. Farmers should be 'allowed to fail', with financing that recognises the risk inherent in many interventions and the importance of trial and error.

Public perspectives of good food must be shifted, encouraging the public to accept that healthier, more sustainable food deserves higher prices, and demonstrating how to eat locally and seasonally. Wider financial changes (e.g. in wages) are needed to give people the agency to purchase healthy and sustainable food, and charismatic and knowledgeable change agents are needed to persuade others (especially those in power) to transform behaviour.

In summary, **regenerative agriculture must be supported in multiple ways, including with knowledge, infrastructure and incentives.**

Good progress is already being made in some domains of H2, whereas in other domains there is insufficient progress and/or currently a lack of action. In many cases a good start has been made in a particular domain but further action is needed to make it more transformative.

H2 domains of strength

- There is a lot happening already in terms of farmers sharing best practice, and the UK government recognises its importance and assists via its Farm Resilience Fund. Online networks are already available for connecting farmers with an interest in regenerative agriculture, such as the BASE-UK forum and Groundswell.
- Farms often generate copious on-farm data that could speed up feedbacks in farming decisions.
- Public awareness of the impact of agriculture on the environment is increasing and the UK has committed to carbon net zero by 2050. There are consequently many companies investing in carbon sequestration opportunities such as changes in farming practices, to satisfy their consumers and net zero agenda.
- The paradigm of agricultural funding is changing to 'public money for public goods'.
- There are some charismatic and influential figures coming on board to back regenerative agriculture (e.g. at Groundswell).

H2 domains of weakness

- There are not enough best practice sharing events targeted to local landscapes (especially in the north), and insufficient independent advice. The sheer volume of data on best practice can become overwhelming without clear methods of prioritisation. Once practice is shared, getting farmers to trial new things is still a major challenge due mainly to lack of trial support from academic community, time constraints and associated risks; profitability is an important driver.
- Despite the high potential for farmers to make the most of their on-farm data beyond accounting purposes, such as for practice-based decision-making, there is low uptake in Britain due mainly to expensive paywalls to access necessary tools, time constraints, and complex online systems. Breaking costs down into simple intuitive units can help.
- There is a lack of scientific research and data providing evidence that changes in practice on-farm have lower negative environmental impacts and sequester carbon, and a significant lack of data on current carbon storage in UK soils and the potential to further sequester carbon. There is also risk in farms selling carbon to another company. The market for regeneratively produced food is poorly structured, with unclear brand differentiation and no standards.
- We need more universal calculators for biodiversity, carbon, etc. so that there is methodological continuity for calculating a standard baseline of public good delivery.

Next steps

We hope that the insights presented in this report will help to guide food system transformation.

Building on this work, next steps for the FixOurFood regenerative farming systems project at the University of Leeds will focus on three areas of activity in Yorkshire:

- 1. Spreading a positive message about the work many farmers are already doing**
- 2. Providing an evidence base for regenerative practice**
- 3. Supporting farmer-led knowledge transfer**

The University of Leeds has a 317 ha research farm to trial and test regenerative farming practices to support evidence-based practice, measuring the impact of changes in practice on soil, crops, profit and greenhouse gas emissions.

Working with the Yorkshire Agricultural Society and through meetings, workshops and on-farm demonstrations we will be supporting farmer-led knowledge transfer as well as spreading a positive message about the transformative systems that already exist in Yorkshire and what we can learn from them.

This work will feed into wider FixOurFood collaboration, such as modelling the impact of changes in practice on global warming with Cranfield University, and policy and governance with City, University of London.

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